

Supplemental Figures

Figure S1 Hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) tolerance of selected safety-certified LAB strains isolated from camel milk. OD_{600} measurements of 16 safety-evaluated LAB isolates from camel milk, *L. lactis* (R1, R3, R5, R6, R8, R9, R10, R11, R13, R15, R16) and *L. mesenteroides* (C1, C4, C5, C10, C11), were obtained following exposure to increasing concentrations of H_2O_2 (0–2.4 mM) for 5 h (blue lines) and 8 h (red lines). Data are presented as mean \pm SEM from three independent biological replicates.

Figure S2 Shelf-life stability of yogurt co-fermented with *Leuconostoc mesenteroides* C8 under ambient temperature. Changes in physicochemical and antioxidant properties of yogurt stored at room temperature (25 °C) for 21 days, comparing the commercial starter (YO-MIX 883) and co-fermented group (YO-MIX 883 + C8). Parameters include: pH (A), titratable acidity (B), viable LAB counts (C), water holding capacity (D), total polyphenol content (TPC) (E), DPPH radical scavenging activity (F), and hydroxyl radical scavenging activity (G). Data are expressed as mean ± SEM (n = 3).